

Development of Physical Qualities through the Training Process of Volleyball Players in a Sports Club

Choliyev Avaz Koldoshevich¹

¹ Navoi State Pedagogical Institute "Methodology of teaching sports" department, etc. associate professor

Abstract:

In the article, the effective use of qualities such as quickness, agility, strength, dexterity, flexibility in the training plan of volleyball players is widely covered. During the training process, athletes are required to have maximum speed, agility, intelligence, quick thinking, ability to quickly understand the situation on the field and give a "useful" response in difficult conditions. The article is intended for volleyball coaches and those involved in this sport.

Keywords: Sports training, static exercises, physical qualities, training, physical training, special training, volleyball.

INTRODUCTION.

Modern volleyball, in its essence, content, and technical-tactical combinations performed at extremely high speed, requires a great physical ability and functional training from the players. Physical and functional training, in turn, is of fundamental importance for the effective formation of sports skills.

It is known that volleyball is one of the most popular sports in our country. At the same time, in all sports schools, the issue of training international-level competitive volleyball players still remains a problem.

For many years, the issues of focusing on children's sports, including volleyball, cultivating talented young volleyball players, creating all-round conditions for them, improving the qualifications of coaches, and training young professionals have been neglected.

Decree No. PF-6099 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 30, 2020 "On measures for the wide implementation of a healthy lifestyle and development in mass sports" and its implementation 'lib determined the "today" and "tomorrow" perspective of this issue and laid the fundamental foundation for its regulatory and material support.

In fact, in recent years, in the development of children's sports in our country, very large reforms have been introduced in terms of training young talented sports reserves, many creative works have been carried out, regular sports activities and local and All conditions have been created for holding competitions at the republic level.

The next issue now and in the near future is to implement the final goals set by the requirements of this Decree and Decision. It is known that the main strategic problem in this area is to create the scientific and methodological basis of training young, competitive athletes. However, in terms of its organizational and technological aspects, this process belongs to the composition of very complex, comprehensive and multifaceted problems, and it is necessary to organize it on the basis of the principles of gradualism and consistency.

It is aimed at studying the effectiveness of using non-standard game exercises in developing some physical qualities (speed, agility, strength, dexterity, agility) that are directly related to the formation of sports skills at the initial stage of training young volleyball players. Of course, many scientific and theoretical opinions and information about pedagogical research in this regard have found their place in many scientific literature (L.V. Byleyeva, I.M. Korotkov 1982; I.M. Korotkov 1971, 1979, 1991; A.I. Lisitsina, T.S. Usmonkho Jayev, 1989; M.N.Kurbonova, 2003. In most cases, it is noticeable that the method of developing sports skills, which is the foundation of sportsmanship, is based on the use of general or special exercises. forcing such exercises can have certain negative consequences.

MAIN PART:

STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT OF PHYSICAL QUALITIES IN VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS BASED ON DIFFERENTIAL METHODS.

Physical training is one of the types of training aimed at developing the volleyball player's body, improving his physical qualities and abilities, and creating a solid foundation for effective performance of the game.

Modern volleyball belongs to the type of sports games that require great strength, speed, agility, endurance and flexibility from the players. A volleyball player's high-speed execution of many blocks, kicks and serve jumps, falls, runs, stops, turns, bends and other movements during each game is a great physical activity. requires strength, extreme agility, strong endurance and mental harmony.

Today's volleyball player with indicators that can quickly understand "useful" answers is 185-195 cm tall, mobile, fast, agile, intelligent, intelligent, quick-thinking, sharp minded, able to understand the situation on the field. it is necessary. Therefore, depending on the age, training, qualification, and the period of sports training and tasks of athletes, the content, size and intensity of physical training will be different.

The tasks of physical training are as follows:

1. Strengthening health.
2. Vital - improvement of necessary movement skills (walking, running, jumping).
3. Development of movement qualities.
4. Increase the volume of movement skills and expand the scope of their execution.

5. Forming the functions of organs, sections and muscle groups of the body participating in the game.
6. Development of special qualities that ensure effective mastering of game skills.

Physical training is divided into two types: general and special physical training.

One of the important tasks of general physical fitness sports training is aimed at ensuring full physical development and all-round physical fitness of the participants. UJT is a process aimed at improving vital movement skills and developing basic physical qualities. Its purpose is to create the base of the UJT, which is the foundation of the MJT.

Its tasks are to develop the basic physical qualities, increase the functional capabilities of the body, expand the scope and executive limits of movement skills, strengthen health, and increase the body's resistance to external and internal negative effects.

Common physical attributes include strength, speed, agility, endurance, and flexibility.

UJT consists of specific physical exercises that develop physical qualities individually or together.

It is advisable to use various sports equipment, equipment, trainers and natural factors during the implementation of UJT.

In some stages and periods of sports training, the size, intensity, direction and structure of UJT exercises and trainings are different.

Special physical training is a process aimed at developing the basic and decisive physical qualities in this sport in order to achieve high results in the chosen sport.

Tasks:

- development of special movement qualities and abilities specific to volleyball (speed, power-speed, agility, special endurance, etc.).
- development of skills necessary for mastering game techniques.
- development of skills necessary for mastering game tactics.

All stages and periods of MJT sports training are used with the help of appropriate standards of size and intensity (L.R. Ayrapetyans, 2006).

State educational standards on physical education for general secondary education include requirements for the quality of the educational process, education and content: the necessary and sufficient level of student preparation, activities in educational institutions and physical education and determines the procedures and mechanisms for evaluating the quality of education.

On the basis of the Law "On Education" and the "National Program of Personnel Training", every educational institution should develop the physical capabilities of students to maintain and strengthen their health in the context of the diversity of educational opportunities. they are obliged to form the foundations of physical culture and even create guaranteeing conditions.

The course "Physical education and training" in general secondary education includes the following:

1. Physical education classes.

2. Extracurricular forms of physical activity: gymnastics held before class, physical moments, dynamic pauses during extended breaks, games.
3. Extracurricular forms of physical training: sports sections, electives, sports competitions, etc.

Materials for sports games are included in the physical education curriculum (volleyball, basketball, handball and separate football).

Exercises, technical and tactical methods, as well as theoretical and practical rules of the game, necessary for teaching volleyball program materials are introduced. Therefore, it is appropriate to organize volleyball training in general schools.

Training of young athletes is a multi-stage complex pedagogical process, which requires the organization of training on a scientific basis. It is important to plan and use the volume and intensity of physical and technical-tactical exercises used in training in accordance with the age, physical and functional capabilities of the participating children. The size, intensity, recovery and duration of these exercises should be based on biological laws.

If the exercise load is too high for the child, this load can have a negative effect on the child's body. On the other hand, if the load is less than the capacity, it is inevitable that the formation process will slow down.

Some teachers-coaches forcefully use special and specialized exercises in order to accelerate the development of physical qualities in a short period of time, to train a qualified athlete faster.

In the practice of sports, there are also cases where similar regular exercises extinguish the interest of a child who has just started playing sports, he loses his passion for sports, and eventually he stops playing sports. Therefore, it is very useful and important to use action games in the training of young athletes, especially in the initial stage of training, to develop physical qualities, to form technical and tactical skills.

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